

3.5+ YEARS OF CHARACTERISING EXOPLANETARY SYSTEMS WITH **CHEOPS**

CHARACTERIZING EXOPLANET SATELLITE

Monika Lendl
Université de Genève
CHEOPS Mission Scientist

BRITE Side of Stars
Vienna
22 August 2024

CHEOPS

CHaracterising ExOPlanet Satellite

Ultra-high precision photometry, *one* star at a time, *one* broad optical passband

(Benz+ 2020, Lendl+ 2020)

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- ◆ 30-cm optical photometric telescope

CHEOPS

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(Benz+ 2020, Lendl+ 2020)

- ◆ 30-cm optical photometric telescope
- ◆ S-Class mission
- ESA-CH partnership
- 11 European Countries

CHEOPS

Characterising ExOPlanet Satellite

Ultra-high precision photometry, *one* star at a time, *one* broad optical passband

(Benz+ 2020, Lendl+ 2020)

- ◆ 30-cm optical photometric telescope
- ◆ S-Class mission
ESA-CH partnership
11 European Countries
- ◆ Pointed mission: characterising exoplanets one at a time

CHEOPS

CHaracterising ExOPlanet Satellite

Ultra-high precision photometry, *one* star at a time, *one* broad optical passband

(Benz+ 2020, Lendl+ 2020)

In-flight performances (Fortier+ in review)

CHEOPS

2014

2019

2023

CHEOPS

Mission adoption

2014

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CHEOPS

Mission adoption

Instrument

testing@ESTEC

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Launch

Soyuz launch VS-23
from French Guyana
Space Center

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science mission start

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- ◆ More than 16'500 orbits of science data
- ◆ More than 250 individual science targets observed
- ◆ Lots of science!

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Start of 1st
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Until 31 Dec 2026
→

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CHEOPS' 90-MIN ORBIT

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CHEOPS' 90-MIN ORBIT

CHEOPS

Science Highlights

COMPOSITION OF SUB-NEPTUNES

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COMPOSITION OF SUB-NEPTUNES

TOI-178

The Sun

TOI-178
V=9.2
Late K-type

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The Sun

TOI-178
V=9.2
Late K-type

Possible co-orbital planet pair?

Leleu+ 2019

TOI.01... 3.7 R_E , 10.3 days

TOI.02... 2.3 R_E , 9.9 days

TOI.03... 2.8 R_E , 6.5 days

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TOI-178
V=9.2
Late K-type

Possible co-orbital planet pair?

Leleu+ 2019

Goal:
Resolve system architecture
11-day continuous observation

TOI.01... 3.7 R_E , 10.3 days
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TOI.03... 2.8 R_E , 6.5 days

TOI-178

Leleu+ 2021, Delrez+ 2023

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TOI-178

TOI.01... 3.7 R_E , 10.3 day ~~X~~

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Leleu+ 2021, Delrez+ 2023

TOI-178

TOI.01... 3.7 R_E , 10.3 day ✗

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+ signal at 3.2 days

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+ signal at 1.9 days

+ signal at 15 days

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+ signal at 20 days

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+ signal at 15 days
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TOI-178

Super-Earths to
mini-Neptunes

On both sides of the radius valley

Unexpected density sequence

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JWST program

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

THIS IS THE COOL STUFF!

Nu 2 Lup

The Sun

Nu2 Lup

***Nu 2 Lup: 2 known
transiting and 1 RV planet
around a naked-eye star***

(Udry+ 2019, Kane+2020)

b...	1.67 R_E	11.6 days
c...	2.9 R_E	27.6 days
d...		107 days

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**Goal: measure precise radii
for planets b and c**

b...	1.67 R_E	11.6 days
c...	2.9 R_E	27.6 days
d...		107 days

NU 2 LUP

Transits of
planet b

NU 2 LUP

Transits of planet b

NU 2 LUP

Transits of planet b

Transits of planet c (and b)

NU 2 LUP

Transit of
planet c (!?!?)

NU 2 LUP

Transit of planet c and d!

A transiting planet with an orbital period of `107 days
around a naked-eye star!

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

THIS IS THE COOL STUFF!

HIP 9618

A K-star with 2 small planets observed by TESS

The Sun

HIP9618

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A K-star with 2 small planets observed by TESS

The Sun

HIP9618

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

Duotransits

HIP 9618: A K-star with 2 sub-Neptunes

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

Duotransits

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October
2019

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

Duotransits

HIP 9618: A K-star with 2 sub-Neptunes

October
2019

October
2021

November
2021

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

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HIP 9618: A K-star with 2 sub-Neptunes

October
2019

October
2021

November
2021

True
period:
52d

LONG-PERIOD PLANETS

Duotransits

HIP 9618: A K-star with 2 sub-Neptunes

A 20d and a 52d period sub-Neptune

GROWING POPULATION

CHEOPS REVEALS MYSTERIOUS WARM MINI-NEPTUNES

ESA's Cheops confirmed the existence of four warm exoplanets with sizes between Earth and Neptune, orbiting their stars closer than Mercury our Sun. These so-called mini-Neptunes are unlike any planet in our Solar System and provide a 'missing link' that is not yet understood. Mini-Neptunes are among the most common types of planets known, and astronomers are starting to find more and more orbiting bright stars.

Internal structure possibilities of mini-Neptunes

#CHEOPS

Stars and planets not to scale

Ulmer-Moll et al., *A&A* 674, A43 (2023)
Osborn et al., *MNRAS* 523, 3069-3089 (2023)
Garai et al., *A&A* 674, A44 (2023)
Tuson et al., *MNRAS* 523, 3090-3118 (2023)

CHARACTERISING ATMOSPHERES

Atmospheric
properties of highly-
irradiated planets*

*insufficient SNR for cool planets

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CHEOPS 4 ATMOSPHERES

ppm-level photometry in single optical bandpass

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Occultation — 21 targets

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ppm-level photometry in single optical bandpass

Occultation — 21 targets

Phase curves — 5 targets

with some thermal emission for ultra-hot Jupiters

CHEOPS 4 ATMOSPHERES

ppm-level photometry in single optical bandpass

Reflection dominated for classical hot Jupiters

with some thermal emission for ultra-hot Jupiters

Occultation — 21 targets

Phase curves — 5 targets

HOT JUPITERS CHARACTERISED

BENCHMARK HOT JUPITERS

HD 209458 b

G0V star
1.15 RJ , 1450K planet
 $V = 7.6$

10 occultations

HD 189733 b

K1V star
1.15 RJ , 1200K planet
 $V = 7.7$

13 occultations

Thermal emission negligible

Precisely measure A_g

Do the planets have
(reflective) dayside clouds?

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Brandeker+ 2022

$$dF_{\text{occ}} = 20 \pm 3.3 \text{ ppm}$$

$$A_g = 0.096 \pm 0.016$$

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Do the planets have
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No!

ULTRA HOT JUPITERS

MASCARA-1 b

WASP-189 b

KELT-20 b

WASP-178 b

KELT-9 b

A8 star, $V = 8.3$

A5 star, $V = 5.6$

A2 star, $V = 7.6$

A1 star, $V = 9.9$

A0 star, $V = 7.55$

1.6 RJ, 2600K planet

1.6 RJ, 3400K planet

1.7 RJ, 2500K planet

1.8 RJ, 3200K planet

1.9 RJ, 4000K planet

3 occultations

6 occultations, 2 PC

7 occultations

6 occultations

10 occultations, 4 PC

ULTRA HOT JUPITERS

MASCARA-1 b

WASP-189 b

KELT-20 b

WASP-178 b

KELT-9 b

High thermal
emission

Large
planet/star
contrast

Observationally
favourable

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1.6 RJ , 2600K planet

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1.6 RJ, 3400K planet

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CHEOPS' first science: 4 occultations

ULTRA HOT JUPITERS

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CHEOPS' first science: 4 occultations

88.6 ± 10 ppm

83.5 ± 10 ppm

94.0 ± 10 ppm

89.3 ± 7 ppm

ULTRA HOT JUPITERS

WASP-189 b

1st CHEOPS obs

Lendl+ 2020

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ULTRA HOT JUPITERS

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Full phase curve

Deline+ 2022

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Lendl+ 2020

Full phase curve

Deline+ 2022

Dayside flux difficult to explain with thermal emission only, $A_g = 0.26$ (0.15)

ULTRA-HOT JUPITERS

MASCARA-1 b

WASP-189 b

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WASP-178 b

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ULTRA-HOT JUPITERS

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CHEOPS & Spitzer

ULTRA-HOT JUPITERS

MASCARA-1 b

WASP-189 b

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CHEOPS & Spitzer

Full phase curve

Deline+ 2022, Hooton+ 2021,
Jones+ 2023, Pagano+ 2024, Singh+ 2024

ULTRA-HOT JUPITERS

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CHEOPS & Spitzer

Variability?

Full phase curve

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CHEOPS & Spitzer

Variability?

High redistribution

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CHEOPS & Spitzer

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CHEOPS, TESS & Spitzer phase curves

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ULTRA-HOT JUPITERS

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Dayside systematically require extra reflected light in CHEOPS passband, $A_g \sim 0.2$

CHEOPS & Spitzer

Variability?

High redistribution

CHEOPS, TESS & Spitzer phase curves

Full phase curve

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WASP-12B TIDAL DEFORMATION

WASP-12

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WASP-12B TIDAL DEFORMATION

Akinsanmi+ 2024

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- Hotspot shifted eastward by winds

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WASP-12B TIDAL DEFORMATION

WASP-12 b

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- Tidally deformed shape:
1.23:1.06:1.0

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PS: DO IT YOURSELF!

Call for CHEOPS Guest Observers every spring

- ◆ Everyone can apply (no restrictions wrt. to countries and institutions)
- ◆ Between cycles: Discretionary Time (DT) available
- ◆ !! Requirements relaxed on DT program for Early-career researchers !!

Thank You!

